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Executive Summary

Nitrogen and carbon cycles are central to soil fertility, ecosystem functioning, and sustainability in Mediterranean agroecosystems such as olive groves. The balance between ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-) interacts closely with soil organic carbon (SOC) dynamics, influencing nutrient availability, microbial activity, greenhouse gas emissions, and long-term soil stability. Nitrification, the microbial transformation of ammonium into nitrate under aerobic conditions, plays a key role in determining nitrogen availability for plants and the risk of environmental losses, including nitrate leaching and nitrous oxide emissions. SOC, both in concentration and stock, serves as a critical indicator of soil quality, affecting structure, water retention, nutrient storage, and carbon sequestration. In Mediterranean olive groves, maintaining healthy SOC stocks is essential to enhance soil resilience, mitigate land degradation, and support sustainable production.

This report assessed soil nitrogen and SOC dynamics across 52 olive orchards in multiple Mediterranean countries, soil samples were collected at two depths (0–10 cm and 10–20 cm) following the LUCAS sampling protocol. Nitrification and ammonification rates were measured through controlled aerobic incubations, while SOC was quantified using both the ISO 10694:1995 dry combustion method and the dichromate wet oxidation method to account for variations in soil carbonate content. Bulk density and coarse fragments were incorporated to calculate SOC stocks, providing an integrated measure of carbon storage across different management systems.

Results showed that conventional orchards generally had higher nitrate concentrations, although values mostly remained below critical thresholds, except in Greek orchards where both conventional and organic systems exhibited elevated nitrate, suggesting potential over-fertilization and increased nitrogen loss. Ammonium concentrations were higher in intensified orchards, particularly in Portugal, likely due to slower nitrification and lower nitrogen availability for plant uptake. SOC stocks were highest in organic orchards and lowest in intensively managed high-density systems, reflecting the impact of management intensity on soil quality. The bimodal distribution of SOC within and across orchard types highlighted the complex interplay between nutrient availability and carbon storage: phosphorus was the main driver in organic and conventional orchards, whereas nitrogen limited SOC accumulation in high-density systems. Method comparisons revealed that SOC measurements can be overestimated by the ISO method in calcareous soils, emphasizing the need to consider soil carbonate content when interpreting results.

These findings underscore the importance of tailoring management practices to the specific nutrient requirements and soil conditions of each orchard type. Optimizing phosphorus and nitrogen inputs has the potential to enhance SOC storage even in intensively managed systems; however, achieving high SOC levels in these orchards will require a broader shift toward more sustainable farming practices.

1. Introduction.

Nitrogen and carbon cycles are fundamental processes that control soil functioning, fertility, and sustainability in Mediterranean agroecosystems such as olive groves. The balance between different forms of nitrogen in soil, particularly ammonium (NH_4^+) and nitrate (NO_3^-), interacts with soil organic carbon (SOC) dynamics to influence nutrient availability, microbial activity, greenhouse gas emissions, and long-term soil stability. Understanding the interactions between nitrogen forms and carbon processes is essential for improving soil management practices and maintaining productive agricultural systems (Ochoa-Hueso et al., 2011; Xiao C., 2015).

Nitrification is a key microbial process in the nitrogen cycle that regulates the transformation of ammonium (NH_4^+) into nitrate (NO_3^-) under aerobic soil conditions. This process determines the relative availability of ammonium and nitrate for plant uptake and strongly influences nitrogen losses through nitrate leaching and emissions of nitrogen-related greenhouse gases, such as nitrous oxide. As nitrate is highly mobile in soils, nitrification plays a central role in nitrogen use efficiency and environmental sustainability in agricultural systems (Robertson and Vitousek, 2009; Robertson & Groffman, 2024).

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a central indicator of soil quality, influencing soil structure, water-holding capacity, microbial activity, and nutrient storage. In addition to SOC concentration, the stock of SOC represents the total amount of carbon stored in the soil and provides an integrated measure of long-term soil fertility and carbon sequestration. In Mediterranean agroecosystems, SOC and its stock are critical for enhancing soil resilience, mitigating land degradation, and supporting sustainable agricultural production (Lal, 2004; Smith et al., 2008).

2. Methods and Materials.

2.1. Sample collection.

A total of 494 soil samples were collected from 52 different olive orchards to assess soil organic carbon (SOC) and nitrification rates, following the LUCAS sampling protocol (Orgiazzi et al., 2018). In each orchard, five georeferenced LUCAS replicates were obtained. Each replicate was composed of five subsamples taken at the LUCAS point and in the four cardinal directions, and sampling was conducted at two soil depths (0–10 cm and 10–20 cm). After collection, soil samples were air-dried and stored under controlled conditions until further laboratory analyses. The theoretical maximum for this sampling design was 520 samples (52 orchards \times 5 replicates \times 2 depths); however, not all field replicates from some Greek and Italian orchards were received for analysis, yielding the 494 samples reported here. The study comprised 52 of the 53 orchards selected in Deliverable D1.1; the orchard ES-HD10 Olmillos was not sampled because the grove had been replanted between the signing of the collaboration agreement and the sampling campaign, and it was therefore excluded from the study (see Deliverable D1.1 for further detail).

2.2. Nitrification rates.

Nitrification and ammonification rates were determined using an aerobic soil incubation method to assess the effect of land-management type on nitrogen mineralization processes. Soil samples were homogenized and incubated at 20 °C at 60% of water-holding capacity (WHC) for a period of 70 days. During incubation, inorganic nitrogen concentrations (NH_4^+ and NO_3^-) were periodically measured following extraction with a saline solution and subsequent colorimetric analysis. Net ammonification, nitrification, and nitrogen mineralization rates were calculated based on changes in ammonium and nitrate concentrations over time.

2.3. Soil organic carbon stock.

Soil organic carbon (SOC) was quantified using two complementary analytical methods. Dry combustion was performed following the ISO 10694:1995 standard (ISO, 1995). Prior to analysis, soil samples were sieved to <2 mm and finely ground. Inorganic carbon was removed by treating the samples with 4 M hydrochloric acid to dissolve carbonates, applying identical acid volumes and reaction times to all samples to ensure consistency. The remaining organic carbon was then measured using a macro elemental analyzer. As dry combustion methods can overestimate SOC in soils with high carbonate contents due to incomplete carbonate removal, SOC was additionally determined using the wet oxidation method described by Nelson and Sommers (1996). This approach selectively oxidizes organic carbon under strongly acidic conditions using potassium dichromate ($\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$), followed by heat-assisted digestion to ensure complete oxidation. The amount of reduced chromium (Cr^{3+}) produced was quantified by molecular absorption spectrophotometry, allowing SOC concentrations to be calculated.

Bulk density was estimated using the pedotransfer functions developed by Saxton and Rawls (2006), based on soil texture (determined according to Bouyoucos, 1928) and soil organic matter (SOM). The empirical approach using Kopecky cylinders was not applied in this study, and coarse fragment fractions were not directly measured. SOC values were converted to SOM using a conversion factor of 1.724, assuming an average carbon content of 58% in organic matter (Pribyl, 2010). Soil organic carbon stocks (SOCs) were calculated following the equation proposed by Poeplau. Because the estimated bulk density returned anomalously high and physically implausible values ($> 3 \text{ g/cm}^3$) for a subset of samples — including those from Morocco and part of the Greek dataset — these were considered unreliable and excluded from the SOC-stock analysis, resulting in a final dataset of 362 samples from 39 orchards.

3. Results.

3.1. Nitrogen.

Figure 1. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NO_3^- among management; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each management with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

In Figure 1, which presents NO_3^- concentrations across olive grove management, we observed significant differences among treatments. The highest values occurred under conventional management, while the intensive orchards showed the lowest concentrations. However, all values remained below the threshold associated with high nitrate availability.

Figure 2. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NO_3^- among country; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each country with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

Figure 3. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NO_3^- across management and country; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each management with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

A similar pattern is evident in Figure 2, except for the Greek orchards, where nitrate concentrations significantly exceeded this threshold, particularly under organic and conventional management (Fig. 3). In these cases, concentrations above 30 mg/kg indicate a high risk of nitrate loss and may signal over-fertilization.

Figure 4. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NH_4^+ among management; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each management with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

Regarding NH_4^+ concentrations presented in Figure 4, the ANOVA revealed significant differences among management systems. Intensified orchards showed the highest mean ammonium concentrations; however, values across all management types remained within ranges typically reported for agricultural soils. This indicates that, despite statistical differences, ammonium levels were not excessively elevated and remained within expected background conditions.

Figure 5. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NH_4^+ among country; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each country with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

Figure 6. Left: Boxplot showing differences of NH₄⁺ across management and country; ANOVA statistics are displayed above. Right: Bar plot showing the mean value for each management with corresponding standard errors. A red threshold line indicates the point beyond which values are considered excessive. (n = 494).

At the country level (Figure 5), NH₄⁺ concentrations generally fell within the expected range across management systems, with the notable exception of Portugal. In this case, elevated ammonium values were observed exclusively in intensified orchards (Figure 6). This localized accumulation of NH₄⁺ may indicate reduced nitrification rates, potentially reflecting lower nitrogen availability for plants and diminished microbial activity under intensified management conditions.

3.2. Soil Organic Carbon stock.

Figure 7. Distribution and correlations among soil organic carbon content methods (ISO and Nelson & Sommers) and carbonate content. (n = 362).

A significant positive correlation was found between the two SOC quantification methods. However, the ISO method also exhibited a significant positive relationship with soil carbonate content, suggesting that direct acid treatment does not fully remove inorganic carbon in highly calcareous soils (Figure 7). This indicates that SOC may be overestimated when using ISO in soils with high carbonate levels.

Fig 8. Comparison between methods for quantifying soil organic carbon and their correlation with carbonate content. (n = 362).

Figure 8 shows that this overestimation by the ISO method becomes more pronounced as soil carbonate content increases. In contrast, the dichromate method slightly overestimates SOC overall, but this effect is minor and mainly observed in low-carbonate soils, where the ISO method provides reliable measurements. These results highlight that method performance depends on soil carbonate content and should be considered when interpreting SOC data.

Fig 9. Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) by Management and Depth. Letters (a, b, c) placed inside each boxplot indicate significant differences among managements, based on Tukey's post-hoc test ($p < 0.05$). Asterisks (* or ***) above boxplot denote significant differences between depths within that specific management. (n = 362).

Significant differences were observed among the three management types, with the highest SOC values found in organic orchards and the lowest in intensified orchards. When comparing different soil depths within each management type, only intensified orchards showed no significant differences, suggesting potential soil degradation and the development of shallow soil profiles under this management system.

Fig 10. Above: SOC stocks across three management systems. Violins show data distribution, boxes indicate IQR, black points are ANOVA-adjusted means (emmeans). F and p-values from ANOVA are shown at the top. Below: Mean SOC for Low and High groups within each management system. Groups are defined by values below (Low) or above (High) the median of the variable causing the strongest bimodality. Bars show mean \pm SE, colored by group. (n = 362; 39 orchards).

Once SOC (determined by the dichromate method), soil depth, coarse fragment content, and bulk density were incorporated, high-density orchards were found to have the lowest overall SOC stock values (Figure 10a). Within each management type, SOC data displayed a bimodal distribution, highlighting the complexity of SOC dynamics in Mediterranean olive groves. SOC stocks displayed a bimodal distribution across management types, with different nutrients driving the observed patterns. In organic and conventional orchards, phosphorus was the main factor associated with the two modes (Figures 10b and 10c), while in high-density orchards, nitrogen primarily explained the bimodal SOC distribution (Figure 10d).

In organic orchards, phosphorus acted as a limiting factor, with higher phosphorus levels associated with higher SOC stocks, supporting the idea that SOC accumulation in these systems depends on phosphorus availability. In contrast, nitrogen played a more prominent role in high-density orchards, where SOC stocks are generally lower and nitrogen often limits SOC storage.

4. Conclusions.

Nitrogen dynamics in Mediterranean olive groves were strongly influenced by management intensity and regional context. Conventional orchards generally exhibited higher nitrate concentrations, though most values remained below critical levels, with the exception of Greek orchards, where both organic and conventional systems showed elevated nitrate, indicating potential over-fertilization and increased risk of nitrogen losses. Ammonium concentrations were also higher in intensified orchards, particularly in Portugal, suggesting slower nitrification and reduced nitrogen availability for crops.

Soil organic carbon stocks were highest in organic orchards and lowest in high-density, intensively managed systems, reflecting a potential for soil degradation under intensive practices. The bimodal distribution of SOC across management types underscores the complex interplay between nutrients and carbon storage: phosphorus was the main driver in organic and conventional orchards, while nitrogen played a larger role in high-density systems. These patterns highlight the importance of adapting management strategies to the specific nutrient and soil characteristics of each orchard. By carefully balancing phosphorus and nitrogen inputs, SOC accumulation can be improved even in intensive systems, though long-term gains will likely require a transition toward more sustainable cultivation practices.

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